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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF *BALACHATURBHADRA CHURNA*

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Abstract

Background: Standardization of the herbal formulation is a critical and essential issue to be considered in assuring the therapeutic efficacy and safety and to rationalize their use in the health care. It is crucial to assess the quality and purity standards of the drug. *Balachaturbhadra Churna* is a reputed poly-herbal formulation of Ayurveda for pediatric disorders. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Balachaturbhadra* was carried out. *Balachaturbhadra* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.). Slides of each ingredient of *Balachaturbhadra* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Balachaturbhadra Churna* shows reticulate xylem vessels and parenchyma, fibers, fragments of metaderm, fragments of thin-walled cells, acicular crystals, epidermal cells, oil cells, cork, phloem parenchyma, starch grains etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Balachaturbhadra* helps in correct identification of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.)

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INTRODUCTION:

Herbal medicines are produced on a large scale in pharmaceutical units, where manufactures face many challenges such as availability of quality raw material, authentication of raw materials, and availability of standards, proper standardization method of individual medicine and formulation and quality control parameters. The increasing demand for the raw materials and unavailability of the resources compel many manufacturers to go for substitutes and adulterants which result in the substandard products. The quality of finished products vary from one pharmacy to another also there is no consistency in batch to batch production of herbal drugs.

It is important to ensure the standard and quality right from the raw drugs to the finished product. So, to detect contaminants and for identification of herbal drug, powder microscopy is essential. Here, for the present study *Balachaturbhadra* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Balachaturbhadra Churna* is a reputed poly-herbal formulation of Ayurveda for pediatric disorders.¹ It contains *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.)

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Balachaturbhadra*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as reticulate xylem vessels and parenchyma, fibers, fragments of metaderm, fragments of thin-walled cells, acicular crystals, epidermal cells, oil cells, cork, phloem parenchyma, starch grains etc. in the powder of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.)
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Balachaturbhadra was used for the powder microscopy. *Balachaturbhadra* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.). Rhizomes of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.), fruits *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), rhizomes of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.) and galls of *Karakatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Balachaturbhadra* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.¹⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Balachaturbhadra Churna*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Musta</i>	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Karkatshringi</i>
1.	Tissue cell	+			
2.	Vessel element	+			

3.	Crystal	+			
4.	Stone cells		+		
5.	Starch grains		+	+	+
6.	Fragments of thin-walled cells		+		
7.	Fibers		+	+	+
8.	Reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma			+	
9.	Fragments of metaderm			+	
10.	Parenchyma cells filled with starch grains			+	
11.	Acicular crystals				+
12.	Epidermal cells				+
13.	Oil cells				+
14.	Cork				+
15.	Phloem parenchyma				+

Table No. 2: Powder microscopic study of *Musta*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Musta</i>	Figure no.
1.	Vessel element with spiral thickening	[Fig. 1.a]
2.	Crystal	[Fig. 1.b]
3.	Tissue cell	[Fig. 1.c]

Table No. 3: Powder microscopic study of *Pippali*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pippali</i>	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Starch grains	[Fig. 2.b]
3.	Fragments of thin-walled cells	[Fig. 2.c]
4.	Fibers	[Fig. 2.d]

Table No. 4: Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ativisha</i>	Figure no.
1.	Reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Starch grains	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Fibers	[Fig. 3.c]
4.	Fragments of metaderm	[Fig. 3.d]
5.	Parenchyma cells filled with starch grains	[Fig. 3.e]

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Karkatshringi*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Karkatshringi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Acicular crystal	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Starch grains	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Epidermal cells	[Fig. 3.b]
4.	Oil cells	[Fig. 3.c]
5.	Fibre	[Fig. 3.d]
6.	Cork	[Fig. 3.e]
7.	Phloem parenchyma	[Fig. 3.f]

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Balachaturbhadra* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Balachaturbhadra* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Musta* shows, Vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue cell and crystal. Powder microscopy of *Pippali* shows stone cell, starch grains, fragments of thin-walled cells and fibers. Powder microscopy of *Ativisha* shows, reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Karkatshringi* shows, acicular crystal, starch grains, acicular crystals, epidermal cell, oil cell, cork and phloem parenchyma.

Standardization of compound Ayurvedic formulations are quite difficult and complicated. But it is necessary to ensure the quality and safety of herbal drugs which makes herbal medicines very useful. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Balachaturbhadra* was carried out and their microscopic characters were noted. These characters might help in detecting impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

Powder microscopic study of *Musta*

Vessel element with spiral thickening

[Fig. 1.a]

Crystal

[Fig. 1.b]

Tissue cell

[Fig. 1.c]

Powder microscopic study of *Pippali*

Stone cell

[Fig. 2.a]

Starch grains

[Fig. 2.b]

Fragments of thin-walled cell

[Fig. 2.c]

Fibre

[Fig. 2.d]

Pharmadaa

Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha*

Reticulate
xylem
vessel and
parenchyma

[Fig. 3.a]

Starch grains

[Fig. 3.b]

Fibre

[Fig. 3.c]

Fragments of
metaderm

[Fig. 3.d]

Parenchyma
cells filled with
starch grains

[Fig. 3.e]

Powder microscopic study of *Karkatshringi*

[Fig. 6.a]

[Fig. 6.b]

[Fig. 6.c]

[Fig. 6.d]

[Fig. 6.e]

[Fig. 6.f]

CONCLUSION:

The current study's finding aid in the identification of *Balachaturbhadra*. According to observations, microscopic characters such as vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue cell and crystal indicates the presence of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.). Microscopic characters such as stone cell, starch grains, fragments of thin-walled cells and fibers indicates the presence of *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.). Microscopic characters such as reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains indicates the presence of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.). Microscopic characters such as acicular crystal, starch grains, acicular crystals, epidermal cell, oil cell, cork and phloem parenchyma indicate the presence of *Karkatshringi* (*Pistacia integerrima* Stew.). Thus, powder microscopy of herbal drug should be carried out before it is introduced in the pharmaceutical market and hospitals for strengthening the health of population.

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